

Physics-based zoning of unconventional aircraft: The swept stroke phase

Nathanael A. Jenkins^{*,#}, Carmen Guerra-Garcia^{*}

^{*}*Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics*

Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Cambridge, MA

[#]*Department of Aeronautics*

Imperial College London

London, UK

¹naj20@mit.edu

²guerrac@mit.edu

Abstract—Lightning zoning is a critical exercise for the design and certification of the lightning protection measures of aircraft. As the aviation industry powers towards a low-emission future, novel zoning methodologies, compatible with non-standard aircraft configurations, need to be devised. Current practices for evaluating the swept stroke region (zone 2) rely on empirical models, which are trusted for ‘tube-and-wing’ concepts, but their validity remains unproven for less conventional, next-generation aircraft. Physics-based models, which are increasingly feasible with modern computing capabilities, have the advantage that they are agnostic to the particular aircraft being considered and theoretically do not require prior experience with that vehicle. Therefore, the use of physics-based models for lightning zoning might be the only path to certify aircraft for which no in-service experience is available. They will also align industry standards for zoning with the state-of-the-art in engineering simulations.

In this contribution, we present a physics-based model for the swept stroke zone, building on previous work which identified initial attachment points (zone 1). The swept stroke is simulated using an idealized lightning arc, which is linearly advected in a flowfield, and realistic flowfields for 3D aircraft models are obtained using computational fluid dynamics (CFD). The proposed tool uses physical models for reattachment and reconnection of the arc and also tracks the delivery of current to the aircraft surface. Any number of arcs can be simulated in parallel, randomly positioned in the first lightning zone. The distributions of attachment probability and dwell time across the aircraft surface can be mapped to identify lightning zones 2A (swept stroke) and 2B (swept stroke with long hang-on).

This work presents results of the swept stroke model for various aircraft configurations. First, data from the NASA Storm Hazards Program is compared to simulated results on the Convair F-106B to validate the behavior of individual lightning arcs and to understand the effect of simulated flight conditions. The model is found to be most sensitive to aircraft attitude, while altitude does not significantly impact results. The Storm Hazards Program data also validates the model’s ability to simulate the distribution of attachment probability over the aircraft surface. Second, a generic commercial aircraft is ‘zoned’ and compared to published zoning diagrams to validate the output of simulations with thousands of arcs, focusing on mapping probability and dwell time data into a zoning diagram. Finally, the model is applied to different unconventional aircraft configurations to demonstrate a zoning result which could not have been achieved

following the current Aerospace Recommended Practices.

Keywords—zoning, numerical zoning, swept stroke, unconventional aircraft

I. INTRODUCTION

Most, if not all, modern commercial aircraft consist of a standard ‘tube-and-wing’ configuration. The needs of lightning protection systems for this configuration are well-understood and a wealth of in-service experience helps to maintain excellent safety standards [1]. However, such experience does not exist for the unconventional configurations proposed as solutions to aviation’s climate impact [2]–[4]. The next generation of novel aircraft will necessitate the modernization of lightning protection standards [5]. Examples of different configurations are shown in figure 1; substantial differences are evident between the ‘tube-and-wing’ aircraft and alternative concepts.

For commercial aircraft, lightning protection measures are designed and tested based on three zones which categorize the probability of lightning attachment to different parts of the aircraft [1]. Descriptions of the lightning zones are given in table I. In-service experience and/or an empirical zone location process is used to identify the zones, according to Aerospace Recommended Practice (ARP) 5414B [1]. This process is well understood for conventional configurations, but it is difficult to validate the empirical zoning process for more complex or unconventional aircraft without conducting costly experimentation or flight testing.

TABLE I
AIRCRAFT LIGHTNING ZONES [1]

1A	First return stroke
1B	First return stroke with long hang-on
1C	‘Transition zone’ for first return stroke
2A	Swept stroke
2B	Swept stroke with long hang-on
3	Areas not included in zones 1 or 2

To resolve this challenge, simulation-based zoning has been proposed; while computational analysis is mentioned in the

Fig. 1. Different aircraft configurations, including conventional and unconventional choices [6]–[9].

context of the initial attachment point [1], ARP 5414B does not discuss computational methods for determining the second lightning zone. Some attempts have been made to develop such models [10]–[12] and this work builds on those efforts, aiming to demonstrate the efficacy of computational tools for such work. Previous efforts have successfully identified the initial lightning attachment points and the first lightning zone using computational analysis [12], [13]; the results from such simulations could serve as an input for the swept stroke model presented in this work.

An automated, geometry-agnostic zoning tool would allow engineers to better understand the lightning protection requirements of new aircraft concepts earlier in the design process, as well as reducing the time and effort required for certification of the lightning protection system. The proposed model can be coupled with existing zone 1 models, as illustrated in figure 2, to complete the automated zoning workflow. The model developed in this work is referred to as the ‘Simulation Workflow for Electromagnetic Effects: Physics-based Zoning’ (SWEEPZ).

II. SWEEP STROKE MODEL

The initial lightning attachment points provide a starting condition for swept stroke simulations. Another model input is the aerodynamic flowfield around the aircraft, which is assumed to be unaffected by the lightning strike and can be computed using computational fluid dynamics. Figure 2 shows how these inputs feed into the SWEEPZ model.

The lightning arc is modeled as a tube with a constant radius and constant internal electric field. It is perfectly advected by the airflow and remains in contact with the surface at all times.

Fig. 2. Simulation workflow for lightning zone 2.

Two key mechanisms are considered during simulations; (1) *reattachment* occurs when the arc stretches over a surface and then jumps to a new attachment point, and (2) *reconnection* describes the closing of loops which can form in the arc. The model is illustrated in figures 3 and 4; the numerical implementation of the model is discussed by Jenkins [14].

Fig. 3. Engineering model for the swept lightning arc.

Fig. 4. Engineering model for reattachment and reconnection of the swept lightning arc.

The aircraft surface is discretized into many thousands of cells based on the mesh used for computational fluid dynamics simulations. The probability of the arc passing through each cell on the surface is recorded during each simulation; for a single arc, this is 100% in regions which experience attachment and 0% everywhere else. The average of this probability is calculated for many thousands of arcs to attain the statistical

distribution of attachment points for the entire aircraft. Another key metric is the dwell time, which is a measure of the time the arc spends in contact with each cell. This is also recorded for every arc simulation and the average is calculated within each surface cell.

III. APPLICATION TO THE NASA STORM HAZARDS PROGRAM

The model was validated using data from the NASA Storm Hazards Program, during which a military aircraft was flown into thunderstorms to observe aircraft-storm interactions [15]. The aircraft was struck by lightning more than 714 times and the swept stroke attachment points were recorded for 17 of these strikes. To the authors' knowledge, these patterns are the only public data set of their kind.

The results of simulated lightning strikes were compared to the Storm Hazards Program data by two means; (1) individual strike patterns, which demonstrated the model's ability to capture certain physical mechanisms and (2) the distribution of many strikes, which showed the model's ability to capture statistical distributions and their sensitivity to simulation parameters. The aircraft in question is a modified Convair F-106B, a military interceptor aircraft with large delta-style wings. The geometric differences between commercial and military aircraft are unlikely to change how the lightning swept stroke behaves, although lightning protection for military aircraft is not assessed by zoning. The comparisons presented in this section are described in more detail in [16].

Figure 5 illustrates the lightning sweeping patterns for a simulated arc (pink tracks) and a similar strike recorded in the Storm Hazards Program (green points). This illustrates the model's ability to emulate the real behavior of the lightning swept stroke, despite its many simplifications. These results also show how a viscous fluid model, which resolves more, but not all, of the flow physics produces less valuable swept stroke data. The lower-fidelity inviscid fluid model actually benefits swept stroke simulations because the slip condition at the wall better emulates the small-scale, near-wall behavior of the arc which is not resolved by a Reynolds-averaged viscous model.

Fig. 5. Simulation results for strike 8 from the 1981 Storm Hazards Program campaign, using different fluid models [16].

Figure 6 further illustrates the inadequacy of the viscous fluid model, which fails to predict lightning attachment in many regions where the Storm Hazards Program experienced

attachment. The surface probability distribution extracted from the inviscid result maps well to the NASA data. Particularly, the region underneath the aircraft canopy experiences a high density of attachment points in the Storm Hazards Program data (green points) which was also modeled by the simulated result. Fisher et al. [17] suggest that the entire F-106B aircraft is at risk of lightning attachment during the swept stroke; this remains a reasonable conclusion based on the simulated data.

Fig. 6. Effects of different fluid models on swept stroke attachment probability distribution, Storm Hazards Program attachment points shown in green [16].

Further simulations of the distribution of many strikes were used to conduct a sensitivity analysis which is discussed by Jenkins [14]. This work found that the aircraft altitude and fixed arc radius were of little importance compared to the aircraft attitude. While yaw angle is rarely significant for a commercial aircraft, most lightning strikes occur during climb or descent [18] when aircraft are likely to be at a non-zero pitch angle. This means that efforts to zone aircraft based on these results must also consider the effects of pitch, and possibly yaw.

IV. APPLICATION TO A CONVENTIONAL AIRCRAFT

Simulations of a generic commercial aircraft were conducted at a speed of 200 ms^{-1} and an altitude of 5000 ft. 6000 lightning strikes were simulated at pitch angles of 0° and $\pm 2^\circ$, considering initial attachment points near the aircraft nose. An additional simulation at 0° pitch was conducted with initial attachment points around the leading edges of the engine cowlings.

The simulation results were translated into lightning zones based on two thresholds. First, zone 2 (including sub-zones 2A and 2B) was identified based on the attachment probability, which is normalized by the square root of cell area to cancel out the effects of the discretization's non-uniform cell sizes. Of the regions within zone 2, those with long hang-on (2B) were identified based on the arc-attachment point average tracking speed; regions with long hang-on will experience much slower tracking speeds. The tracking speed is given by the inverse of the average dwell time within each cell, normalized by the square root of cell area for dimensional consistency. The values of these thresholds were calibrated using simulations of a commercial aircraft and were chosen to be $P_{\text{attachment}} < 0.025 \text{ m}^{-1}$ and $U_{\text{tracking}} < 8U_\infty \text{ ms}^{-1}$, where U_∞ is the true airspeed. The probability threshold can be interpreted by considering a 1m wide strip on the aircraft

surface; if more than 2.5% of all lightning strikes could pass through that strip, it belongs in zone 2.

The simulated zoning diagram in figure 7 is similar to published diagrams for commercial aircraft, an example of which can be found in Sweers, Birch and Gokcen [19]. The entire fuselage is recognised as zone 2A using both methods, with some extension on to aerodynamic surfaces at the root of the wing and tailplane. While the ARP dictates a 0.5 m extension at these regions, the simulated result experienced a broader extension up to 1.3 m from the fuselage, in the case of the wing root at label (a). However, this is likely to be a symptom of the initial conditions which extended arcs in any direction in the hemisphere in front of the nose. This meant that arcs were simulated from the aircraft nose extending in the direction of the wing; these arcs would most likely attach to the wing tip [20] and not the aircraft nose, so the simulated result is more conservative than required. This artifact will likely disappear when the zone 2 model is connected to the zone 1 model.

Fig. 7. Simulated lightning zones 2 and 3 for a commercial aircraft with attachment at the nose only, considering pitch angles of 0° , $\pm 2^\circ$. Also consider attachment to the engine cowling at 0° pitch.

Although attachment to the engine cowling has only been simulated at 0° pitch, the zoning result near the engines in figure 7 is similar to published diagrams [19]. The underside of the wing near the engine remains in zone 3, while the zone

2 region on the engine cowling is projected onto the upper wing surface, highlighted by label (b). Future simulations will be conducted at different pitch angles to refine the zoning diagram in this region.

Both the commercial zoning result and the unconventional aircraft illustrated in figure 8 experience one phenomenon which differs from existing zoning practises; a region of long hang-on (zone 2B) appears on the underside of the fuselage taper near the aft of the aircraft, at label (c). At low or negative pitch angles, the tapered underside of the fuselage begins to behave like a trailing edge and the arc will begin to sweep slower, or even stop sweeping, in this region. The severity of the hang-on here is dictated by the angle of the taper. It is unclear why the current standard does not account for this in the zone identification workflow, so further investigation will be necessary to determine whether long hang-on does indeed occur at this location.

Fig. 8. Simulated lightning zones 2 and 3 for a truss-braced wing aircraft with attachment at the engine and the nose, considering pitch angles of 0° , $\pm 5^\circ$, and $\pm 10^\circ$.

V. APPLICATION TO A TRUSS-BRACED WING

Having validated this methodology by comparing results to flight data and existing standards, the tool was applied to an unconventional, 'truss-braced wing' aircraft. The zoning mapping based on 6000 simulations of lightning arcs at 0° , $\pm 5^\circ$, and $\pm 10^\circ$ are illustrated in figure 8. This result considers

initial attachment points at the aircraft nose and the leading edges of the engine cowlings, distributed within the anticipated zone 1 region based on ARP 5414B [1].

The result in figure 8 is largely consistent with the requirements of existing recommended practises. The sides of the fuselage at label (a) experience substantially reduced attachment probabilities, since the lightning arcs which would otherwise be swept over this region are intercepted by the wing or its truss and experience long hang-on at the trailing edges without reattaching to the fuselage. While there may be scope for reducing lightning protection in this region, the patchy nature of the result suggests that, although reduced, the attachment probability remains close to the threshold for zone 2.

Another interesting feature is the projection of the swept stroke region from the engine cowling onto the underside of the truss at label (b), a phenomenon which is not explicitly accounted for in existing recommended practices, as they do not contemplate the existence of a truss. The simulated result also dictates that the majority of the wing and truss trailing edges (and some leading edges) should be zone 2, despite the surface in front of them being zone 3; this is highlighted with label (c). This is caused by the relatively extreme pitch angles used in the simulation. At high pitch ($+10^\circ$), the arc is not swept over the wing surface and the leading edge behaves like a trailing-edge surface, experiencing much higher attachment probabilities which the model recognises as zone 2. At low pitch (-10°), the trailing edge surfaces dominate and also experience much higher attachment probabilities. These conditions are unlikely to occur for a commercial aircraft, except in cases of serious upset, so may not apply to zoning considerations. This highlights the importance of considering only standard pitch angles when zoning computationally.

Figure 9 illustrates how a truss which meets the underside of the wing at a non-zero angle can induce a small zone 2 region because it contracts the paths of the arcs ahead of the truss; many low attachment probability regions merge into one higher-probability region aft of the joint. Existing standards do not account for this, but the phenomenon may warrant increased protection near joints of this nature.

Fig. 9. Simulated lightning zoning at the underside of the wing-truss joint for a truss-braced wing.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

A physics-based model for the lightning swept stroke has been presented and its results mapped to aircraft lightning zones. The model is verifiable [14] and valid based on comparisons to data from the NASA Storm Hazards Program. The zoning mapping has been calibrated based on a conventional aircraft zoned using Aerospace Recommended Practices and produces similar results to the current state-of-the-art.

The proposed model has been applied to an unconventional ‘truss-braced wing’ aircraft and produced results which could not be attained using current standards. Three phenomena were identified which current standards do not consider; (1) the projection of the swept stroke zone aft of the engine and onto the wing truss, (2) the concentration of swept stroke patterns near the wing-truss joint leading to a thin zone 2 region, and (3) reduced tracking speed along the underside of the fuselage taper increasing hang-on in this region. These observations will be confirmed by simulations including more lightning arcs and improved statistics.

Future work to integrate physics-based models for all lightning zones would allow for improved initial conditions in the swept stroke model and would enable the automation of the aircraft zoning process. The computational efficiency of this tool can be improved by GPU parallelization to significantly reduce simulation time. Further experimental validation of this tool, as well as investigations into the magnetohydrodynamic behavior of the swept arc at small scales could be of value to this work, particularly when considering the use of computational tools for aircraft certification and regulatory approval.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to extend thanks to Qiqi Wang, Samuel Austin, Jaime Peraire and Ngoc Cuong Nguyen for their support of this work, as well as Louisa Michael and Ben Westin. The authors acknowledge the Imperial College London Department of Aeronautics, MIT SuperCloud and Lincoln Laboratory Supercomputing Center for providing high-performance computing resources that have contributed to the research results reported within this work.

REFERENCES

- [1] “Aircraft Lightning Zone,” Dec. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sae.org/standards/content/arp5414b/>
- [2] JetZero, “JetZero Unveils Ultra-Efficient Blended Wing Body Aircraft for the Airline Middle Market,” Apr. 2023.
- [3] Airbus, “Hybrid and electric flight,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.airbus.com/en/innovation/low-carbon-aviation/hybrid-and-electric-flight>
- [4] Rolls Royce, “Pioneering Electrification,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rolls-royce.com/products-and-services/electrical.aspx>
- [5] C. Guerra-Garcia, “The Role of Low Temperature Plasma Research in Designing the Lightning and Precipitation Static Protection of Novel Aircraft,” *IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science*, vol. 51, no. 4, pp. 965–979, Apr. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9916641/>
- [6] N. A. Jenkins, “CAD Models,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://nathanaelj.github.io/Projects/Modelling#F-106B>
- [7] Helijah, “Bell Boeing V22 Osprey,” 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://skfb.ly/yrOW>
- [8] Annelida, “VTOL Air Taxi,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/vtol-air-taxi-ecb6d12a90514aab9105061a34c7d604>

- [9] M. Kruger, "Blended Wing Body," GitHub, Feb. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/danielenriquez59/vsp-gmr/tree/59b5eae1947f67ffdae11f87637fa07d0d6a850/models/BWB>
- [10] A. Larsson, P. Lalande, A. Bondiou-Clergerie, P. Lalande, and A. Delannoy, "The lightning swept stroke along an aircraft in flight. Part I: thermodynamic and electric properties of lightning arc channels," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 33, no. 15, pp. 1866–1875, Aug. 2000. [Online]. Available: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/0022-3727/33/15/317>
- [11] A. Larsson, P. Lalande, A. Bondiou-Clergerie, and P. Lalande, "The lightning swept stroke along an aircraft in flight. Part II: numerical simulations of the complete process," *Journal of Physics D: Applied Physics*, vol. 33, no. 15, pp. 1876–1883, Aug. 2000. [Online]. Available: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/0022-3727/33/15/318>
- [12] P. Lalande and A. Delannoy, "Numerical Methods for Zoning Computation," *AerospaceLab Journal*, no. 5, Dec. 2012.
- [13] S. P. Austin, C. Guerra-Garcia, and J. Peraire, "Computational Zoning of Unconventional Aircraft," in *International Conference On Lightning and Static Electricity (ICOLSE)*, Madrid, Spain, Oct. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7155575>
- [14] N. A. Jenkins, "Numerical Simulation of the Lightning Swept Stroke for the Zoning of Unconventional Aircraft," Master's thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology and Imperial College London, 2024.
- [15] B. D. Fisher and J. A. Plumer, "Lightning attachment patterns and flight conditions experienced by the NASA F-106B airplane from 1980 to 1983," in *22nd Aerospace Sciences Meeting*. Reno, NV, U.S.A.: American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Jan. 1984. [Online]. Available: <https://arc.aiaa.org/doi/10.2514/6.1984-466>
- [16] N. A. Jenkins and C. Guerra-Garcia, "Numerical Simulation of the Lightning Swept Stroke: Application to the Results from the NASA Storm Hazards Program," 2024, to be submitted.
- [17] B. D. Fisher, P. W. Brown, J. A. Plumer, and L. C. A. J. Wunschel Jr, "Final Results of the NASA Storm Hazards Program," in *International Conference On Lightning and Static Electricity (ICOLSE)*, Oklahoma City, Oklahoma, Apr. 1988.
- [18] V. A. Rakov and M. A. Uman, *Lightning: physics and effects*. Cambridge, U.K. ; New York: Cambridge University Press, 2003.
- [19] G. Sweers, B. Birch, and J. Gokcen, "Lightning Strikes: Protection, Inspection, and Repair," *AERO*, no. 48, 2012. [Online]. Available: www.boeing.com/commercial/aeromagazine/articles/2012_q4/pdfs/AERO_2012q4.pdf
- [20] S. P. Austin, "Computational Zoning Assessment of Unconventional Aircraft," SM Thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Boston, USA, May 2022.